

POWER GENERATION ANALYSIS WITH COMPRESSED AIR STORAGE SYSTEM

S.M. Swamy¹ and G.P.Prasada Reddy²

G. Narayanamma Institute of Technology and Sciences, Shaikpet, Hyderabad, India.

Abstract: Power generation from renewable energy has become more important due to the increase of electricity demand and pressure on tough emission reduction target. This has brought great impact on grid reliable operation. Wind curtailment often happens when grid cannot accommodate more wind power. Among all the ES technologies, Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) has demonstrated its unique merit in terms of scale, sustainability, low maintenance and long life time. A wind turbine is a device that converts wind energy into rotational energy using blades called vanes. Typically, wind turbines are connected to electrical generators to produce electricity directly. In this study, a wind turbine-compressed air storage system is explored. The stored compressed air powers the air turbine consistently. An alternator is attached to the turbine rotor shaft. Some of the rotor's power is converted to electricity using the alternator, while the rest is used to operate the compressor, producing compressed air that is stored in a tank. This stored air is then used to drive the air turbine and generate electricity without fluctuations. The paper is to provide an overview of the current research trends in CAES and also update the technology development.

Key Words: Compressed Air Storage, Wind Turbine, Renewable energy, Wind velocity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Among various renewable energy resources, wind energy is one of the fastest growing technologies in India. Even though wind energy is an intermittent source of energy and it is not completely reliable. Actions must be taken to increase the reliability of wind energy. The wind has dynamic behavior. Sometimes the wind velocity is more than what is required, and in sometimes it is very less. During high wind, the amount of excess energy produced through wind is not used and hence wasted. To address this issue, a strategy needs to be employed to exploit the use of excess wind at times when there is not enough wind to meet the demand. One of the solutions is to install compressed air storage technologies at wind farms. These storage technologies would serve the purpose of storing compressed air during excess energy produced through wind. The energy produced using the compressed air could then be used to make up the mismatch between wind generation and the load during times when the wind is not able to serve the load completely.

Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) is one of the most reliable energy storage technologies for wind farms. Among other storage technologies, CAES is known to have one of the highest power and energy rating. During off-peak hours, an air compressor driven by an electric motor is fed the excess amount of power produced through wind. The compressor compresses the air and stores it inside an air storage tank. The storage tank can be underground or above the ground.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup consists of a six bladed rotor, a compressor, an air storage tank, an air turbine and an alternator. The compressor and the fan are fitted on a single mild steel pipe column. The fan blades are made of 1.5mm thick mild steel sheet. Six blades are fixed at 30° inclination for smooth flow of air. The widths of the blade at the fixed end and free end bottom are 100mm and 150mm respectively.

The air tank and the air turbine are fitted on the base of the setup. The pressure gauge and the pressure relief valve are fitted on the air tank in order to release excess air when the air pressure exceeds the tank withstand pressure. The tube is used to connect the compressor outlet and the air tank inlet. Two alternators of 12 Volt and 24 Volt capacities are used for producing power. 24 Volts capacity alternator is coupled with the air turbine shaft and 12 Volts capacity alternator is coupled with the shaft of the fan for producing

electrical energy.

In the present work the wind turbine rotor is coupled with a reciprocating air compressor. When the wind turbine rotor rotates, the air compressor compresses the air, and this compressed air is stored in the air storage tank. The stored compressed air is used to run the air turbine.

Fig. 1 Compressed air generation and storage setup.

The photographic views of the wind turbine based compressed air generation and storage setup are shown in Figure 1.

Compressed air storage tank	Length of the cylinder	50 cm
	Diameter of the cylinder	30 cm
	Capacity of the tank	16.84 liters
	Maximum pressure of the tank	5 kg/cm ²
	Number of cylinders	2
	Cylinder position	Horizontal
Alternator Capacity	Direct coupled alternator	12 Volt, 15 Watts, 1.2amps
	Turbine alternator:	24 Volt, 30 Watts, 1.2 amps
Compressor	Type	Reciprocating
	Bore diameter	60 mm diameter
	Stroke length	80 mm length
	Cubic capacity	226.29 mm ³

Table.1

3. PRINCIPLE OF WORKING OF WIND TURBINE OPERATED COMPRESSOR

The wind energy with the required velocity (15 to 25 km/hr.) in the atmosphere is forced to rotate the fan. As the fan rotates, the reciprocating air compressor coupled with the shaft of the fan and compresses the air and the compressed air is stored in the storage tank to run the air turbine for future energy generation. The remaining part of the available energy in the shaft is used to convert into electrical energy using an alternator, which is fitted with the shaft of the fan. The direct coupled alternator produces electricity with 10 to 25 volts according to the speed of the shaft that depends on air velocity. The stored compressed air is used to run the air turbine, and the alternator which is coupled with the shaft of the air turbine generates 12 volts of electrical energy.

3.1 Experimental Procedure

The wind velocity is measured using vane anemometer, and the time taken to increase the air pressure in every 1 kg/cm² in the air tank is observed using a stop watch until the tank pressure reaches 6 kg/cm². Thereafter the stored compressed air is released to rotate the air turbine. The multi-meter is used to measure the voltage generated by the two alternators, one is coupled with the shaft of the fan and another one is coupled with the air turbine.

Fig.2. Vane anemometer, stop watch and multi meter.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The vane anemometer is used to measure the air velocity and pressure gauge fitted in the air tank is used to measure the air pressure in the storage cylinder. The multi meter is used to find the voltage generated by the alternator.

The wind velocity is 25 km/hr, the fan shaft rotates with a speed of 200 rpm. Figure 4 shows the variation of air pressure rise in the storage tank with respect to time. It is seen from the figure that the air pressure in the storage increases linearly with respect to time. The time taken to reach 6 kg/cm² pressure in the storage tank is 39 minutes.

Fig. 3. Variation of cylinder pressure with respect to time

Fig. 4 Variation of voltage generation with respect to wind velocity

Figure 5 shows the variation of voltage generated by the alternator connected with the shaft of the fan with respect to wind velocity. It is seen from the figure that the generated voltage increases with an increase in wind velocity, and it reaches 12 volts when the velocity of the wind is 25 km/h.

5. CONCLUSION

The attempt of the present work deals with a wind mill with compressed air storage for dual power production. In the present work, in addition to direct production of power by wind mills, a reciprocating air compressor is coupled with the shaft of the fan to produce compressed air. The stored compressed air is utilized to run the turbine to produce electricity. The alternator is coupled with the shaft of the fan is used for converting the remaining mechanical energy available in the shaft of the wind mill in to electrical energy.

Energy storage provides an opportunity to grasp and balance the wind energy as it is produced. It may be stored and used later when the demand is expected to increase the capacity of wind energy production. This technology is pollution free and makes the environment clean and reduces the need for future conventional power plants.

- Generally, wind mills produce power and supply it directly to the usage. But in the present setup, the part of the developed mechanical energy is stored in the form of compressed air. The stored compressed air is used for power generation during the demand period.
- Power produced in two ways. Hence the efficiency of the system is more.
- Compressed air can be used for various purposes like water pumping; running pneumatic based equipment, etc.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alan T. Zehnder and Zellman Warhaft (27 July 2011). "University Collaboration on Wind Energy". Cornell University Atkinson Center for a Sustainable Future. Retrieved 22 August 2011.
- [2] Johnson, Scott J.; van Dam, C.P.; Berg, Dale E. (2008). "Active Load Control Techniques for Wind Turbines". Sandia National Laboratory. Retrieved 13 September 2009.
- [3] "Vestas world's largest wind turbines". Renewable energy focus.com. 2010-10-24. Retrieved 2013-11-06.
- [4] Navid Goudarzi. "A Review on the Development of the Wind Turbine Generators across the World". International Journal of Dynamics and Control, Vol.1, pp. 192 – 202, 2013.
- [5] Wang, S.; Lai, X.; Cheng, S. An analysis of prospects for application of large-scale energy technology in power systems. Autom. Electr. Power Syst. 2013, 37, 3–8. [CrossRef]
- [6] Li, J.; Tian, L.; Lai, X. Outlook of electrical energy storage technologies under energy internet background. Autom. Electr. Power Syst. 2015, 39, 15–25.
- [7] Xu, Y.; Chen, H.; Liu, J. Performance analysis on an integrated system of compressed air energy storage and electricity production with wind-solar complementary method under energy internet background. Proc. CSEE 2012, 32, 88–95.
- [8] Liu, C.; Xu, Y.; Hu, S.; Chen, H. Techno-economic analysis of compressed air energy storage power plant. Energy Storage Sci. Technol. 2015, 4, 158–168.
- [9] China Energy Storage Alliance Steering Committee. Energy Storage White Paper 2016; China Energy Storage Alliance: Beijing, China, 2016.
- [10] Luo, X.; Wang, J.; Ma, Z. Overview of energy storage technologies and their application prospects in Smart Grid. Smart Grid 2014, 2, 7–12.
- [11] Sameer, H.; Johannes, L. A review of large-scale electrical energy storage. Int. J. Energy Storage 2015, 39, 1179–1195.
- [12] Kousksou, T.; Bruel, P.; Jamil, A.; Rhafiki, T.; Zeraouli, Y. Energy storage: Applications and challenges. Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cell. 2014, 120, 59–80. [CrossRef]
- [13] Mahlia, T.M.I.; Saktisahdan, T.J.; Jannifar, A.; Hasan, M.H.; Matseelar, H.S.C. A review of available methods and development on energy storage; technology update. Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev. 2014, 33, 532–545. [CrossRef]
- [14] Zakeri, B.; Syri, S. Electrical energy storage systems: A comparative life cycle cost analysis. Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev. 2015, 42, 569–596. [CrossRef]
- [15] Geng, X.; Zhu, Q.; Guo, H.; Duan, C.; Cui, H. Energy storage technology and application in Power system. Smart Grid 2016, 4, 54–59